

Navigating the Challenges of CAP Strategic Planning in the EU

CAP implementation faces numerous challenges including complex multi-level governance, insufficient capacity among staff and stakeholders, and obstacles to evidence-based policymaking. Poor coordination between national and regional authorities often results in policies disconnected from local needs, while limited expertise hinders implementation. A report by the Tools4CAP project calls for clearer guidelines, inclusive decision-making, capacity building, and tools to improve stakeholder engagement and policy outcomes. By enhancing data infrastructure and fostering collaboration among diverse groups, more sustainable CAP Strategic Plans can be developed. Tools4CAP offers methodologies and resources to address these challenges and improve future decision-making and monitoring processes. Op-ed by Simone Sterly and Carla Wember (both Institute for Rural Development – IfLS).

As the European Union embarks on a new chapter in its Common Agricultural Policy (CAP), the complexities of decision-making and governance have never been more pronounced. The recent report from the **Tools4CAP project** highlights critical challenges faced by Member States in designing and implementing CAP Strategic Plans (CSPs). These challenges not only threaten the efficacy of agricultural policies but also the sustainability of rural communities across Europe.

[Read/download Tools4CAP-Report on co designed improved or new decision making tools](#)

The Complexity of Multi-Level Governance

One of the most significant hurdles identified is the intricate web of multi-level governance that characterises the CAP. With responsibilities spread across national and regional authorities, coordination often falters. Stakeholders report difficulties in aligning objectives and ensuring that local needs are adequately represented at

the national level. This disconnect can lead to policies that are out of touch with the realities faced by farmers and rural communities.

The report underscores the urgent need for clearer guidelines and streamlined processes. As Member States grapple with the volume and complexity of CAP documents, the lack of transparency in decision-making exacerbates frustrations. Stakeholders frequently feel sidelined, leading to a democratic deficit in policy formulation. To foster genuine stakeholder engagement, it is imperative that decision-making processes are not only transparent but also inclusive.

Figure: Study result on challenges in CAP Strategic Plan design (number of mentions in focus groups, literature reviews and online survey) Source: Tools4CAP

Capacity Building: A Path Forward

Another pressing issue is the lack of capacity among ministry staff and stakeholders. Many officials lack the necessary expertise to navigate the evolving landscape of CAP regulations. This skills gap hampers effective policy implementation and monitoring. The report suggests that investing in capacity building is essential for empowering decision-makers and ensuring that they can engage meaningfully with stakeholders.

Innovative tools, such as multi-criteria analysis and cumulative voting, have shown promise in enhancing stakeholder participation and prioritising needs. These methods can help bridge the gap between complex policy frameworks and the practical realities of agricultural governance. By equipping stakeholders with the right tools and knowledge, we can create a more responsive and effective CAP.

Embracing Evidence-Based Policy Making

The report also highlights obstacles to evidence-based policy making, often hindered by political contestation and path dependencies. To overcome these barriers, it is crucial to foster a culture of collaboration and open dialogue among all stakeholders. This includes not only farmers and agricultural organizations but also environmental groups and civil society. A holistic approach to policy design that considers diverse perspectives will lead to more sustainable outcomes.

Moreover, the integration of robust data collection and analysis into the decision-making process is vital. As the report indicates, many Member States struggle with data coverage and relevance. By investing in better data infrastructure and ensuring that stakeholders have access to relevant information, we can enhance the quality of policy decisions and their implementation.

Conclusion: A Call to Action

As the preparations for the next funding period are starting, it is time to put these insights into action. Addressing these challenges through structured methodologies and inclusive practices can significantly enhance the effectiveness of CSP design and monitoring. Tools4CAP aims to provide CAP decision-makers with suitable tools for a more evidence-based policy making, ultimately improving capabilities to design next-generation CSP, and to perform monitoring tasks to review performance of implementation and beneficiary compliance. The project prepares guidelines and builds capacities on methods such as participatory vision building, process communication and stakeholder engagement, Intervention-Objectives-Impact (IOI) matrix, intervention logic, prioritisation and decision making, and scenario building for policy impact assessment (PIA).

This text builds on two deliverables of the T4C project:

- Report on key challenges for decision making across EU MS
- Report on co-designed improved or new decision-making tools

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